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LYME DISEASE, PREVALENCE IN UKRAINE, MODERN PRINCIPLES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.

Abstract

Khvoroba Layma – poshyrena infektsiya, shcho peredayet'sya iksodovymy klishchamy. Zbudnykom ye spirokhetoy Borrelia. Naybil'she vypadkiv reyestryuyut' z travnya po zhovten' cherez aktyvnist' klishchiv ta perebuivannya lyudey na pryrodi. Meta doslidzhennya – vyvchennya epidemiolohiyi, diahnozyky ta terapiyi khvoroby Layma v Ukraini. V Ukraini borelioz klasyfikuyet'sya yak osoblyvo nebezpechna infektsiya, z pidvyshchennyam zakhvoryuvanosti u lisostepoviy zoni. Hrupu ryzyku skladayut' lyudy, shcho chasto perebuivayut' na pryrodi abo pov'yazani z lisovymy zonamy profesiyno. Klinichna kartyna Laym-boreliozu riznomanitna i zalezhyt' vid stadiyi ta imunitetu patsiyenta. Pershyy symptom – erythema migrans. Bez likuvannya khvoroba perekhodyt' u druhu stadiyu z urazhennyam nervovoyi, sertsevo-sudynnoyi system, bolyamy v suhlobakh. Tretya stadiya – khronichna forma z artrytom, entsefalopatiyeu, poliradykulonevrytom ta dermatolohichnymy zminamy. Diahnozyka bazuyet'sya na klinichniy otsyntsi, anamnezi ta laboratornykh testakh. Vazhlyvy kryteriy – nayavnist' erythema migrans. Osnovnyy metod – serolohichni testy ELISA, pidtverdzeni Western blot. U vypadkakh urazhennya nervovoyi systemy doslidzhuyut' spynnomozkovu ridynu. Dlya pidtverdzhennya aktyvnoyi infektsiyi vykorystovuyut' PLR. Likuvannya boreliozu spryamovane na znyschennya zbudnyka antybiotyky. Vybir antybiotyky, dozy ta tryvalosti zalezhyt' vid stadiyi khvoroby, viku patsiyenta ta urazhen' orhaniv. Na ranniy stadiy pryznachayut' doksytsyklin, amoksytsylin abo tsefuroksymu aksetyl. Pry urazhenni nervovoyi systemy, sertsya abo oporno-rukhozhoho aparatu – tseftriakson, tsefotaksim abo penitsylin G.

Keywords: Lyme disease, transmissible infection, ixodid ticks, spirochetes

Lyme disease is the most common vector-borne infection recorded among the population of temperate regions and is transmitted through the bites of Ixodes ticks.

The causative agent of the disease is spirochetes belonging to the genus *Borrelia*.

According to statistical data, the largest number of cases is recorded in the period from May to October, which is explained by both the increased activity of ticks and the increased time that people spend outdoors during this season [1,11].

The purpose of the study:

The study aims to investigate the peculiarities of epidemiology, modern methods of diagnosis and therapy of Lyme disease in Ukraine by analyzing scientific publications, clinical protocols and statistical sources.

Materials and methods.

The analysis was based on official clinical guidelines, publications from medical forums, and information posted on the web resources of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine.

Etiology and distribution:

The etiologic factor of Lyme disease is *Borrelia*, a spirochete from the genus *Borrelia*, which is transmitted to humans by the bite of *Ixodes* spp. These arthropods most often live in grassy areas, forests, city parks, and green spaces. In Ukraine, borreliosis is classified as a particularly dangerous infection.

There is an increase in the incidence in the forest-steppe zone, especially in Kyiv, Lviv, Sumy, Ternopil, Vinnytsia, Cherkasy, and Chernihiv regions. People who are often outdoors or professionally associated with forest areas (foresters, hunters, farmers, shepherds, military personnel, veterinarians, and those who collect mushrooms, berries, etc.) are at increased risk of infection [1,3,11].

Clinical manifestations of Lyme disease:

Lyme borreliosis is characterized by a multifaceted clinical picture that depends on the stage of the disease and the reactivity of the patient's immune system. In most cases, the first symptoms appear 1-2 weeks after the tick bite, although the incubation period can vary from several days to one month. The first and most characteristic clinical manifestation of the early stage of the disease is erythema migrans - redness of the skin at the bite site, which gradually expands, forming a typical "target-like" appearance. This lesion is pathognomonic for Lyme disease and occurs in approximately 60-80% of infected individuals.

Along with localized changes, general symptoms of intoxication are often observed, such as fever to subfebrile or febrile levels, weakness, headache, arthralgia, and muscle pain. Without proper treatment, the disease can progress to the second stage, which is characterized by damage to the nervous system (neuroborreliosis),

cardiovascular system (borreliosis cardiopathy), and the development of migratory joint pain.

The third stage, or chronic form of borreliosis, can develop months or even years after the initial infection. It is accompanied by the persistence of *Borrelia* in the body and manifests itself in the form of chronic arthritis, encephalopathy, polyradiculoneuritis, and dermatological changes - chronic atrophic acrodermatitis.

The course of Lyme disease often depends on the individual characteristics of the organism, as well as on the type of *Borrelia* that caused the infection. For example, *Borrelia burgdorferi sensu stricto* is more often associated with the development of arthritis, while *Borrelia garinii* is associated with neurological damage. [7,8,10]

Diagnosis of Lyme disease:

Effective diagnosis of borreliosis is based on a comprehensive approach that includes clinical assessment of symptoms, anamnesis (especially information about the tick bite), and laboratory tests. An important diagnostic criterion is the presence of erythema migrans, which, in the presence of a characteristic history, allows for a preliminary diagnosis even without laboratory confirmation.

Serological tests are the main method of laboratory diagnosis of Lyme disease. The most widely used methods are enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) to detect antibodies to *Borrelia burgdorferi*, which appear in the blood serum approximately 2-4 weeks after infection. ELISA tests are highly sensitive, but due to the possibility of cross-reactions with other infections, they need to be confirmed by a more specific method - Western blot.

In cases of neurologic disease, it is advisable to examine the cerebrospinal fluid to determine the intracerebral synthesis of antibodies against borrelia. To confirm active infection, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) can also be used to detect pathogen DNA in various biological materials such as blood, skin, cerebrospinal fluid or synovial fluid.

Despite the availability of highly accurate methods, the interpretation of laboratory test results should be based on the clinical picture and epidemiologic history. In some cases, false-negative or false-positive interpretation of the results is possible, which necessitates a thorough clinical analysis. [2,5,6,9]

Treatment of Lyme disease:

Borreliosis therapy is aimed at eradicating the pathogen and preventing the development of complications, and is based mainly on the use of antibacterial drugs. The choice of antibiotic, its dose and duration of treatment depend on the stage of the disease, the patient's age and the presence of lesions in various organs and systems.

At the early stage of the disease, when there is a migratory erythema without systemic manifestations, oral antibiotics are usually prescribed. The most commonly used are doxycycline, amoxicillin, or cefuroxime axetil. The duration of therapy is on average 14-21 days.

In cases where the infection affects the nervous system, heart, or musculoskeletal system, it is advisable to use parenteral forms of antibiotics, such as ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, or penicillin G. The course of treatment can last up to 28 days, depending on the severity of the clinical picture.

After antibiotic therapy, most patients recover completely. However, in some cases, residual symptoms, such as fatigue, muscle or joint pain, called post-borreliosis syndromes, may persist. This condition is not an indication of active infection and does not require a second course of antibiotics, but only symptomatic treatment and rehabilitation measures.

Particular attention in therapy should be paid to patients with concomitant diseases or allergies to antibiotics, as this requires individualized drug selection and careful monitoring of the course of treatment. [1,3,4,8,9]

Conclusions: Lyme disease is a rather severe and dangerous infectious disease, the choice of treatment regimen depends on the diagnostic data and clinical manifestations of the disease. Timely and adequate antibiotic therapy is key to preventing the progression of Lyme disease. Today, there are fairly clear recommendations for antibiotic therapy regimens at different stages of Lyme borreliosis, which have been shown to be effective in numerous clinical trials.

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